

ROLE OF THE ADMINISTRATIVE OFFICER (AO) IN THE PERFORMANCE OF PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS IN KORONADAL CITY

Hazel Grace M. Mallon, Engr. Nathaniel D. Naanep, PhD

Sultan Kudarat State University, Tacurong City, Sultan Kudarat, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15486918>

ABSTRACT

In today's dynamic educational landscape, efficient administrative operations are vital for sustaining effective school management. This study employed a quantitative approach, using descriptive and correlational research designs to evaluate the extent to which administrative officers perform their roles and how this influence overall school administrative performance. The study involved 149 respondents; teachers, school heads, and administrative officers; from District 2 of Koronadal City Division for the school year 2024-2025. Findings revealed that administrative officers performed their roles to a considerable extent with a mean of 4.00. Among the five functional areas, Personnel Administration ranked highest with a mean of 4.18, indicating strong engagement in core duties like record-keeping and document processing. Conversely, Compensation and Benefits scored the lowest with a mean of 3.42, highlighting a need for improved systems in handling benefits and salary adjustments. Regarding school administrative performance, percentage of fund utilization received a perfect score across schools, while monthly liquidation emerged as the weakest indicator with a mean of 2.86, suggesting lapses in timely financial reporting. A statistically significant relationship ($t = 5.60$) was found between administrative officers' performance and school administrative effectiveness, confirming their essential role in institutional efficiency. Challenges such as data management issues, communication barriers, and limited professional growth were also identified, emphasizing the need for enhanced administrative systems, policy support, and capacity-building programs.

Keywords: *administrative officers, school administration, personnel management, fund utilization, performance evaluation, Koronadal City Division.*

INTRODUCTION

In the ever-evolving landscape of educational institutions, the efficacy of administrative operations plays a significant role in promoting a conducive learning environment. The intricate dynamics between management committee support and the administrative functions within schools are essential for the overall success of educational institutions.

Globally, the administrative support and school performance is diverse, shaped by various educational systems, policy frameworks, and cultural contexts (Rodriguez, 2023). Decentralized and centralized administrative models coexist globally, with policies influencing curriculum, assessments, and accountability measures impacting administrative structures (Moloney, 2021). Resource disparities, technological integration, professional development, and community involvement play crucial roles, contributing to varied administrative effectiveness. Regions emphasizing accountability and transparency tend to exhibit efficient administrative systems, while adaptability to crises is pivotal for navigating global challenges (Rosales, 2021).

In the Philippines, the administration of schools was overseen by the Department of Education (DepEd), the primary government agency responsible for managing basic education. The education system followed a decentralized model, with regional and division offices playing a pivotal role in overseeing schools at the local level. School-Based Management (SBM) was a significant aspect of the educational framework, emphasizing decentralized decision-making and involving school stakeholders in governance, resource allocation, and policy implementation. School administrators, particularly principals, was tasked with diverse responsibilities, including curriculum implementation, personnel management, financial oversight, and community engagement, ensured adherence to DepEd policies and the achievement of educational objectives.

The rural schools often faced significant challenges, including resource constraints, overcrowded classrooms, and disparities in educational quality (Philippine Education: Situationer, Challenges, and Ways Forward, 2023). While ongoing reforms, seeking to improve education standards, school administrators continued struggle with limited support in resource management and professional development (Jones & Smith, 2020). Research underscores the importance of administrative support in promoting school improvement and achieving educational goals (Mustafa et. al. 2023), but without consistent coordination and backing from higher-level officers, school administrative performance is compromised. With the recent deployment of administrative officers to handle operational tasks, it was crucial to examine their support's impact on school administration to identify specific needs and inform policy development (Junio, 2024).

While studies underscored the importance of administrative backing in enabling effective school management (Mustafa et. al. 2023), limited research has focused on the nuanced challenges faced by school administrators in remote or disadvantaged areas. According to Junio (2024), existing frameworks often overlook the unique resource limitations and cultural dynamics in these contexts. Additionally, Jones and Smith (2020) highlighted that administrative support needs vary widely, the suggested that a more localized understanding of administrative assistance was necessary.

Therefore, this study sought to address the gap by examining how administrative officers' support impacts the performance of school administrators in rural settings, which can inform tailored policy interventions.

Research Questions

The study determined the extent of Administrative Officers support and the level of school administrative performance as well as their relationship in public elementary school in District 2 of Koronadal City Division during the school year 2024-2025.

Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. To what extent do administrative officers perform their roles in terms of:
 - 1.1 Personnel Administration;
 - 1.2 Compensation and Benefits;
 - 1.3 Other Human Resource related functions;
 - 1.4 Property Custodianship; and
 - 1.5 General Administrative Support?
2. What is the level of school administrative performance in terms of:
 - 2.1. Timely Submission of Report;
 - 2.2 Funds Utilization;
 - 2.3 Liquidation; and
 - 2.4 Awards Received?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of Administrative Officers' roles and level of school administrative performance at 0.05 level of significance?
4. What are the issues, concerns, and problems in the extension of support to school administration?

METHODOLOGY

Locale of the Study:

The study was conducted in the City Schools Division of Koronadal- District II, City of Koronadal. District II was composed of 7 schools. Each 5 schools have one Administrative Officer except the 2 schools which is supervised by one Administrative Officer. This choice of research locale was based on the relevance to the study's focus

on administrative support and school administrative performance within the public elementary school in Koronadal City.

Respondents of the study:

The respondents of this study were the one hundred thirty-three (136) teachers, seven (7) school heads, and six (6) administrative officers from the City Schools Division of Koronadal during the school year 2024-2025. They were chosen because of their direct participation in the providing support to the school.

Sampling Technique:

This study employed complete enumeration. All teachers, administrative officers and school heads who met the primary inclusion criteria was taken as respondents for this study. According to Israel (1992), complete enumeration works best for populations of 200 or fewer people. Complete enumeration yields information on every member of the population and removes sampling error. Finally, to reach a desired degree of precision, small populations would need to be sampled from the entire population.

Data Gathering Instruments:

This study utilized research instrument for teachers, administrative officers and school heads. The instruments were researcher-made survey tools designed to gather relevant data on the roles of administrative officers. The instrument was composed of two (2) parts. Part I covered the roles of administrative officers (AOs), while Part II focused on the issues and concerns encountered in performing the roles of administrative officers.

To ensure consistency in measurement, the researcher used a 5-point Likert scale to rate the extent of the administrative officer's support.

Statistical Treatment:

This study utilized descriptive and correlation statistics. Descriptive statistics was used to determine the extent of administrative officer's support and the level of school administrative performance (mean and standard deviation); and issues, concerns and problems in the extension of support to school administration (ranking). The correlation statistic was used to determine the significant relationship between the extent of administrative support and level of school administrative performance using Pearson r .

RESULTS

Table 1: Summary of Extent of Administrative Officers Perform their Roles

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Personnel Administration	4.18	0.44	Considerable extent
2. Other Human Resource Related Functions	4.14	0.50	considerable extent
3. Property Custodianship	4.03	0.52	considerable extent
4. General Administrative Support	3.73	0.48	considerable extent
5. Compensation and Benefits	3.42	0.74	moderate extent
Grand Mean	4.00	0.37	considerable extent

Table 2: Summary of Points Earned by Schools Level of Performance

Indicators	School							TOTAL
	School A	School B	School C	School D	School E	School F	School G	
1. Timely Submission of Reports	43	31	41	39	45	35	33	35.14
2. Percentage of Fund Utilization	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
3. Percentage of Monthly Liquidation	4	2	2	2	6	2	2	2.86
4. Awards Received	8	8	8	8	12	8	8	8.57
TOTAL	65	51	61	59	73	55	53	59.57
Interpretation	Good	Fair	Good	Good	Very Good	Good	Fair	Good

Table 3: Correlation Analysis Between Extent of Administrative Offices Roles and Level of School Administrative Performance

Variable	df	r	r ²	t _{computed}	t _{critical}	Interpretation
Extent of Administrative Officers Role						
Vs.	147	0.42	17.64%	5.60	1.96	Low Positive
School Administrative Performance						
TOTAL						

$\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance

Table 4: Summary of Ranking Results in the Issues, Concerns and Problems in the Extension of Support to School Administration

Issues, Concerns and Problems	Frequency	Ranking
1. Ineffective Data Management	57	1.5
2. Communication Barriers	57	1.5
3. Technology Integration Challenges	48	3 rd
4. Limited Professional Development Opportunities	47	4 th
5. Staffing Issues	36	5.5
6. Inadequate Facilities and Infrastructure	36	5.5
7. Overloads	32	7 th
8. Limited Autonomy in Decision Making	29	8 th
9. Increasing Administrative Demands	24	9 th
10. Complex Compliance and Reporting	9	10 th

DISCUSSION

Table 1 reveals that the highest-rated area on the role of administrative officers is Personnel Administration, with a mean of 4.18 and a low standard deviation (SD) of 0.44, indicating consistent and strong performance in managing personnel-related responsibilities. Closely following are Other HR Related Functions (mean = 4.14) and Property Custodianship (mean = 4.03), both also rated to a considerable extent, suggesting that administrative officers are reliable in carrying out human resource tasks and managing school property, with moderately low SDs reflecting stable performance.

On the lower end, General Administrative Support received a mean of 3.73, still within the considerable range but with room for improvement, particularly in carrying out additional tasks and supporting planning activities. The lowest-rated area is Compensation and Benefits, which obtained a mean of 3.42 and the highest SD of 0.74, indicating more variation and challenges in tasks like computing benefits, processing adjustments, and preparing reports. Despite these discrepancies, the overall mean of 4.00 and a relatively low SD of 0.37 suggest that administrative officers are generally fulfilling their roles well, though targeted support and capacity building may be beneficial in specific areas like compensation management and general administrative responsiveness.

The findings conformed to Yidana et al. (2023), who posited that administrative support was a critical factor influencing teacher retention, instructional quality, and overall school effectiveness. Their research highlighted its importance in mitigating teacher stress, particularly in rural and challenging contexts where mentorship, guidance, and resource provision played pivotal roles. Differentiated support, tailored to the career

stages of teachers such as targeted feedback for early-career educators and leadership opportunities for seasoned professionals had been shown to improve retention rates and foster professional growth (Tran & Smith, 2019). Moreover, strong administrative support directly impacted on instructional quality by enabling access to professional development and alleviating non-teaching burdens, thereby fostering an environment conducive to effective teaching practices (Yidana et al., 2023).

Table 2 presents the summary of points earned by each school based on key performance indicators and provides a comprehensive view of how administrative functions are being executed across schools. Among the indicators assessed, Percentage of Fund Utilization stands out with all schools earning a perfect score of 10, reflecting strong consistency in how financial resources are allocated and utilized according to plans. Similarly, Awards Received shows relatively high and uniform scores across most schools, contributing positively to their overall performance.

On the other hand, percentage of monthly liquidation is the weakest-performing indicator, with a low overall average of 2.86 out of a possible higher score. This suggests challenges in timely financial reporting or documentation of expenditures, which could be an area for focused improvement. Timely submission of reports shows more variance, ranging from a high of 45 (School E) to a low of 31 (School B), indicating that while some schools are highly compliant, others may require better tracking systems or support mechanisms.

In terms of total performance, School E leads with a total score of 73, earning a Very Good rating, while School B and School G scored the lowest at 51 and 53 respectively, both rated as Fair. The overall average score across all schools is 59.57, interpreted as Good, which suggests that while most schools are performing adequately, strategic efforts to enhance monthly liquidation practices and ensure timely report submission could elevate overall performance further.

The need to strengthen internal controls and enhance monitoring mechanisms is crucial, as effective financial oversight ensures transparency and accountability, which are essential for sustainable school operations (Brigham & Ehrhardt, 2021). Furthermore, encouraging participation in excellence-driven initiatives can help foster a culture of continuous improvement and professional growth. According to Cameron and Quinn (2020), organizations that actively engage in performance recognition programs tend to develop a more motivated workforce and achieve higher institutional success. Similarly, Kaplan and Norton (2019) emphasized that structured performance monitoring and reward systems drive efficiency and accountability in organizations, including educational institutions.

Table 3 showed the relationship between the Extent of Administrative Officers' Role and School Administrative Performance was analyzed using correlation analysis. The results indicate a correlation coefficient (r) of 0.42, suggesting a low/slightly positive relationship between the two variables. This means that as administrative officers perform their roles more effectively, school administrative performance tends to improve. However, the relationship is not perfect, implying that other factors may also influence

school administrative performance.

The coefficient of determination (r^2) is 17.64%, indicating the variance in school administrative performance can be explained by the extent to which administrative officers perform their roles. The remaining is likely influenced by other variables such as leadership effectiveness, resource availability, and institutional policies.

The computed t-value of 5.60, which exceeds the critical t-value of 1.96 at the 0.05 significance level, indicates a statistically significant relationship between the performance of administrative officers and overall school administrative performance. This finding suggests that the effectiveness of administrative officers plays a crucial role in shaping the efficiency and functionality of school operations.

According to Armstrong and Taylor (2020), strong administrative support within educational institutions enhances operational efficiency by ensuring timely reporting, effective resource management, and adherence to institutional policies. Similarly, Berman et al. (2019) highlight that administrative personnel serve as the backbone of school management, influencing overall performance through structured planning, documentation, and compliance with educational standards.

Table 5 presented the analysis of issues, concerns, and problems in school administration reveals key challenges that significantly impact operational efficiency. The most pressing issue is ineffective data management.

Communication Barriers, which highlighted the difficulties in information flow, coordination, and clarity among stakeholders, ranked first among the concerns. Effective communication was crucial for smooth school operations, and miscommunication between school heads, administrative officers, and teachers often led to inefficiencies in policy implementation and decision-making (Robbins & Judge, 2020). Therefore, strengthening communication channels and implementing clear protocols could have helped mitigate this issue.

The third-ranked were Technology Integration Challenges, which suggested that administrative personnel struggled with adopting and utilizing digital tools effectively. Limited access to technology, inadequate training, and resistance to change hindered the efficiency of administrative processes (Schunk & DiBenedetto, 2021). To address this, structured digital literacy programs and improved infrastructure were necessary to enhance administrative efficiency and streamline reporting procedures.

The fourth-ranked concern, Limited Professional Development Opportunities, underscored the need for continuous learning and capacity-building initiatives for administrative officers. Research suggested that ongoing professional development improved administrative competency and adaptability to evolving policies and demands (Guskey, 2020). Without access to relevant training, personnel struggled with policy compliance and efficient school management.

Additionally, staffing issues (5th), Inadequate Facilities and Infrastructure (6th) and Overloads (7th) emphasized the physical and workload-related constraints that impacted administrative officers. A lack of sufficient resources and excessive workloads led to inefficiencies, reduced productivity, and burnout (Maslach & Leiter, 2019). Thus, schools needed to prioritize resource allocation and workload management strategies to support administrative personnel.

Other significant concerns included Limited Autonomy in Decision-Making (8th), Increasing Administrative Demands (9th), and Complex Compliance and Reporting Requirements (10th). These issues suggested that administrative officers operated within restrictive environments, faced growing bureaucratic burdens, and navigated complex regulatory requirements, all of which hindered their efficiency and job satisfaction (Hoy & Miskel, 2021).

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The administrative officer extended very good support. The study also highlights the crucial role of administrative officers in ensuring efficient school operations, particularly in personnel administration, where they excel in record-keeping, leave processing, and documentation. However, challenges persist in compensation and benefits administration, suggesting the need for process improvements and training.
2. School administrative performance is rated as good, with strengths in timely report submission and financial management. However, delays in fund liquidation and limited recognition for performance indicate areas for improvement.
3. There is a significant relationship between administrative officers' performance and overall school efficiency confirms their vital contribution to effective school management.
4. Key challenges include ineffective data management, communication barriers, technology integration issues, and limited professional development. Other concerns such as excessive workloads, staffing shortages, and increasing administrative demands further impact efficiency.

Recommendations

1. School Administrators may implement targeted capacity-building programs. These programs should focus on compensation and benefits administration, as well as property custodianship and general administrative support, where variability in execution was observed.
2. Investing in regular training on financial management, policy implementation, and technological integration may help administrative officers manage the complexities in fund utilization, liquidation, and compliance with reporting requirements.
3. Strengthening internal monitoring systems and performance recognition initiatives can improve school administrative performance, ensuring more timely submission of reports and increased accountability.

4. The school may develop an online data management system to enhance data banking pertaining to administrative tasks.
 5. Future Studies on the impact of specific issues and concerns on the performance of Administrative Officer may be conducted.
-

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers, declares that this research is in compliance with obtaining informed consent, the respondents' freedom to withdraw from the study at any time, anonymity of the respondents was maintained, the respondents' well-being was safeguarded, no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there is no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research.

Acknowledgments

The researcher expresses his gratitude to Sultan Kudarat State University Graduate school, the Schools Division Office of Koronadal, and 136 teachers, 7 school heads and 6 administrative officers of District II of Schools Division of Koronadal City.

REFERENCES

- Armstrong, M., & Taylor, S. (2020). *Armstrong's handbook of human resource management practice* (14th ed.). Kogan Page.
- Berman, E. M. (2019). *Public administration in Southeast Asia: Thailand, Philippines, Malaysia, Hong Kong, and Macao*. CRC Press.
- Brigham, E. F., & Ehrhardt, M. C. (2021). *Financial management: Theory & practice* (16th ed.). Cengage Learning.
- Cameron, K. S., & Quinn, R. E. (2020). *Diagnosing and changing organizational culture: Based on the competing values framework* (3rd ed.). Jossey-Bass.
- Guskey, T. R. (2020). *Evaluating professional development*. Corwin Press.
- Hoy, W. K., & Miskel, C. G. (2021). *Educational administration: Theory, research, and practice* (10th ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.
- Israel, G. D. (1992). *Determining sample size*. University of Florida Cooperative Extension Service, Institute of Food and Agriculture Sciences, EDIS.
- Jones, G. R., & Smith, M. (2020). *Organizational theory, design, and change* (8th ed.). Pearson.
- Junio, N. F. (2024). *The implications of immediate removal of administrative tasks of public school teachers: Basis for transition framework*. Universidad de Manila.
<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28297.86888>
- Kaplan, R. S., & Norton, D. P. (2019). *The balanced scorecard: Translating strategy into action*. Harvard Business Review Press.
- Maslach, C., & Leiter, M. P. (2019). *Burnout: The cost of caring*. Malor Books.
- Moloney, K. (2021). *Rethinking public relations: Persuasion, democracy and society* (3rd ed.). Routledge.

- Mustafa, A., Ali, M., & Yousaf, A. (2023). Role of administrator in school improvement at secondary level: A qualitative study. *Pakistan Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 11(2), 398–413. <https://doi.org/10.52131/pjhss.2023.1102.0398>
- Philippine Education: Situationer, Challenges, and Ways Forward. (2023). Department of Education. <https://pidswebs.pids.gov.ph/CDN/document/pidsdps2223.pdf>
- Robbins, S. P., & Judge, T. A. (2020). *Essentials of organizational behavior* (15th ed.). Pearson.
- Rodriguez, M. (2023). Administrative support and school performance: A global perspective. *International Journal of Educational Leadership and Policy*, 12(3), 211–230.
- Rosales, L. K. G. (2021). Technology integration: Implication for teachers' professional development. In *The Southeast Asian Conference on Education 2021 Official Conference Proceedings* (pp. 1–2). Ateneo de Manila University, Philippines.
- Schunk, D. H., & DiBenedetto, M. K. (2021). Self-regulation and learning. In D. H. Schunk & M. J. Greene (Eds.), *Handbook of self-regulation of learning and performance* (2nd ed., pp. 1–33). Routledge.
- Taylor, L. (2020). The role of administrative support in teacher retention. *Educational Leadership*, 78(1), 45–58.
- Tran, H., & Smith, D. A. (2019). Insufficient money and inadequate respect: What obstructs the recruitment of college students to teach in hard-to-staff schools. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 57(2), 152–166. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEA-10-2017-0162>
- Yidana, M. B., & Arthur, F. (2023). Exploring economics teachers' efficacy beliefs in the teaching of economics. *Cogent Education*, 10(1), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2023.2156558>